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Sobolevning $L_2^{(2)}(0,t)$ fazosida Abel umumlashgan integral tenglamasini yechish uchun optimal koeffitsiyentlar va optimal kvadratur formulaning normasi

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Annotatsiya Ushbu maqolada Sobolev fazosidagi Abelning umumlashgan integral tenglamasini taqribiy yechish uchun vaznli murakkab optimal kvadratur formula qurilgan. Bu kvadratur formulaning optimal koeffitsiyentlari topilgan. Bundan tashqari, qurilgan vaznli murakkab optimal kvadratur formulaning normasi topilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Integral tenglama, optimal kvadratur formula, xatolik funksionali, norma, optimal koeffitsiyentlar

Kirish

Umumlashgan Abel integral tenglamasi birinchi turdagi Volterra chiziqli integral tenglamasining xususiy holidir. Umumlashgan Abel tenglamasi bevosita fizika, mexanika va boshqa fanlarning biror aniq masalasiga olib keluvchi integral tenglamalardan biridir. Differentsial tenglamalarga oid ko'pgina masalalarni integral tenglamalarning qiymatlaridan keltirib chiqarish mumkin. Bugungi kunda tabiatshunoslikning ko'pgina sohalarida Abel tipidagi chiziqli integral tenglamalarni yechishga olib keluvchi masalalar keng tarqalgan. Abel tipidagi tenglamalarga har doim alohida e'tibor berilgan. Bir qator ishlar ushbu sinf tenglamalari yechimlarining mavjudligi, yagonaligi, turg'unligiga bag'ishlangan. Bugungi kunga kelib Abel tipidagi birinchi tur integral tenglamalarni sonli yechishga bir qator yondashuvlar ishlab chiqilgan va keng qo'llanilmoqda.

Shuni ta'kidlash joizki, S.L.Sobolev, V.L.Vaskevich va H.M.Shadimetov [1-3] larning ishlarida panjarali kvadratur va kubatur formulalarni optimallashtirish masalasi ko'rib chiqilgan. V.V. Ivanov [4,5] ning ishlarida singulyar integrallarni hisoblashni optimallashtirish masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Regulyar va singulyar integrallarni taqribiy hisoblash uchun optimal formulalarni qurish B.G.Gabdulxaev [6], I.V.Boykov [7], M.I.Israilov, H.M.Shadimetov, A.R.Hayotovlarning ishlarida davom ettirilgan[8-9].

Ushbu maqolada umumlashgan Abel integral tenglamasini taqribiy yechish uchun optimal kvadratur formula qurish va ularning xatolik funksionallarini differentsiallanuvchi funksiyalar sinflarda normalarini hisoblangan.

Ma'lumki ushbu

$$f(x) = \int_0^x \frac{\varphi(s)ds}{(x-s)^\alpha}, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1$$

tenglama Abelning umumlashgan integral tenglamasi deyiladi. Bu yerda $f(x)$ -mahlum funksiya, $\varphi(s)$ esa integral ostidagi nomahlum funksiya.

$L_2^{(2)}(0,t)$ fazoda optimal koeffitsiyentlar va optimal kvadratur formulaning normasi

Ushbu bo'limda $\rho = 0$ va $m = 1$ holida topilgan optimal koeffitsiyentlar, yahni

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[0] = \frac{t^\alpha}{\alpha} + \frac{h^{-1}}{\alpha(\alpha+1)} \left((t-h)^{\alpha+1} - t^{\alpha+1} \right), \quad (1)$$

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] = \frac{h^{-1}}{\alpha(\alpha+1)} \left[(t-h(\beta+1))^{\alpha+1} - 2(t-h\beta)^{\alpha+1} + (t-h(\beta-1))^{\alpha+1} \right], \quad (2)$$

$$\beta = 1, 2, \dots, N-1.$$

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[N] = \frac{h^\alpha}{\alpha(\alpha+1)}. \quad (3)$$

formular bilan aniqlanuvchi
koeffitsiyentlarni ushbu formulaga qo'yib,

$$\|l_N | L_2^{(m)*} \|^2 = (-1)^m \left[\sum_{\beta=0}^N \sum_{\nu=0}^N \sum_{\nu'=0}^{\rho} C^{(\nu)}[\beta] C^{(\nu')}[\beta'] (-1)^{\nu'} G_m^{(\nu+\nu')}[\beta-\beta'] - \right. \\ \left. -2 \sum_{\beta=0}^N \sum_{\nu=0}^{\rho} (-1)^{\nu} C^{(\nu)}[\beta] f_m^{(\nu)}[\beta] + K_m \right] \quad (4)$$

xatolik funksionali normasining kvadrati uchun
hosil qilingan ifodani $\rho = 1$ va $m = 2$ holida
 $\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta]$, $\beta = 0, 1, \dots, N$ koeffitsiyentlar bo'yicha
minimumlashtiramiz.

Bu holda biz quyidagi kvadratur formulani
qaraymiz

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\varphi(x) dx}{(t-x)^{1-\alpha}} \cong \sum_{\beta=0}^N \left(\overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] \varphi[\beta] + C^{(1)}[\beta] \varphi'[\beta] \right). \quad (5)$$

U holda (4) xatolik funksionali normasi
kvadratining ko'rinishi quyidagicha bo'ladi

$$\|l_N | L_2^{(2)} \|^2 = \left[\sum_{\beta=0}^N \sum_{\nu=0}^N \sum_{\nu'=0}^1 (-1)^{\nu'} C^{(\nu)}[\beta] C^{(\nu')}[\beta'] G_2^{(\nu+\nu')}[\beta-\beta'] \right. \\ \left. -2 \sum_{\beta=0}^N \sum_{\nu=0}^1 (-1)^{\nu} C^{(\nu)}[\beta] f_2^{(\nu)}[\beta] + \frac{t^{2\alpha+3}}{[\alpha+3]!(2\alpha+3)} \right] \quad (6)$$

Bu yerda

$$G_2^{(\nu+\nu')}(x) = \frac{x^{3-\nu-\nu'} \text{sign} x}{2(3-\nu-\nu')!},$$

$$G_2^{(\nu+\nu')}[\beta-\beta'] = \frac{(h\beta - h\beta')^{3-\nu-\nu'} \text{sign}(h\beta - h\beta')}{2(3-\nu-\nu')!},$$

$$f_2^{(\nu)}[\beta] = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=0}^{3-\nu} \frac{(-1)^{\nu+j} (h\beta)^{3-\nu-j} t^{\alpha+j}}{(3-j-\nu)! [\alpha+j]!} + \frac{(t-h\beta)^{3-\nu+\alpha}}{[\alpha+3-\nu]!} \quad (7)$$

$$[\alpha+3]! = \alpha(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)(\alpha+3),$$

$$[\alpha+j]! = \alpha(\alpha+1)\dots(\alpha+j),$$

$$[\alpha+3-\nu]! = \alpha(\alpha+1)\dots(\alpha+3-\nu),$$

$$\text{Bu holda } (l_N(x), x^k) = 0, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, m-1$$

shartlar quyidagi ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] = \frac{t^{\alpha}}{\alpha}, \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta](h\beta) + \sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] = \frac{t^{\alpha+1}}{\alpha(\alpha+1)}. \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta](h\beta) = \frac{t^{\alpha+1}}{\alpha(\alpha+1)} \quad \text{ni hisobga}$$

olsak

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] = 0. \quad (10)$$

Shunday qilib, $\overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta]$ (6) norma kvadratini
(10) shart asosida $C^{(1)}[\beta]$ koeffitsiyentlar bo'yicha
minimumlashtiramiz. Buning uchun, odatdagidek
Lagranj funksiyasini tuzamiz

$$\Lambda(C^{(1)}[\beta], \lambda_1) = \|l_N | L_2^{(2)} \|^2 + 2\lambda_1 \left(\sum_{\beta=0}^N C^{(1)}[\beta] - 0 \right)$$

Xususiylarni hisoblab va nolga tenglab,
quyidagini topamiz

$$\frac{\partial \Lambda(C^{(1)}[\beta], \lambda_1)}{\partial C^{(1)}[\beta]} = 0, \quad \beta = 0, 1, \dots, N,$$

$$\frac{\partial \Lambda(C^{(1)}[\beta], \lambda_1)}{\partial \lambda_1} = 0$$

Bu tengliklar bizga $\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta]$ va λ_1 larni
aniqlash uchun chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar
sistemasini beradi

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] \frac{|h\beta - h\beta'|}{2} + \lambda_1 = f_2^{(1)}[\beta] + \sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] \frac{(h\beta - h\beta')^2 \text{sign}(h\beta - h\beta')}{4},$$

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] = 0.$$

Belgilash kiritamiz

$$F_1[\beta] = f_2^{(1)}[\beta] + \sum_{\beta'=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta'] \frac{(h\beta - h\beta')^2 \text{sign}(h\beta - h\beta')}{4},$$

(11)

bu yerda

$$f_2^{(1)}[\beta] = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=0}^2 \frac{(-1)^{j+1} (h\beta)^{2-j} t^{\alpha+j}}{(2-j)! [\alpha+j]!} + \frac{(t-h\beta)^{2+\alpha}}{[\alpha+2]!},$$

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta], \beta = 0, 1, \dots, N \text{ lar esa (1)-(3)}$$

formulalardan aniqlanadi.

$h\beta \notin [0, t]$, da $\overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] = 0$ deb olib, sistemani svyortka tenglama ko'rinishda yozamiz

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] * \frac{|h\beta|}{2} + \overset{\circ}{\lambda}_1 = F_1[\beta], \beta = 0, 1, \dots, N,$$

(12)

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] = 0, h\beta \notin [0, t], \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] = 0. \quad (14)$$

Belgilash kiritamiz

$$V[\beta] = \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] * \frac{|h\beta|}{2} + \overset{\circ}{\lambda}_1$$

Ma'lumki

$$V[\beta] = F_1[\beta], h\beta \in [0, t].$$

Endi $[0, t]$ kesmadan tashqarida $V[\beta]$ ni aniqlaymiz. $h\beta < 0$ bo'lsin, u holda (14) ni hisobga olib

$$V[\beta] = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\gamma] (h\beta - h\gamma) + \overset{\circ}{\lambda}_1 = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\gamma] (h\gamma) + \overset{\circ}{\lambda}_1 = a_0^-.$$

$h\beta > t$ bo'lsin, u holda (14) ga asosan

$$V[\beta] = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\gamma] (h\beta - h\gamma) + \overset{\circ}{\lambda}_1 = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\gamma=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\gamma] (h\gamma) + \overset{\circ}{\lambda}_1 = a_0^+.$$

Shunday qilib

$$V[\beta] = \begin{cases} a_0^-, & \text{npu } h\beta < 0, \\ F_1[\beta], & \text{npu } h\beta \in [0, t], \\ a_0^+, & \text{npu } h\beta > t, \end{cases}$$

bu yerda a_0^- va a_0^+ lar noma'lumlar.

$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta]$ koeffitsiyentlar quyidagi formula bo'yicha aniqlanadi

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] = hD_1[\beta] * V[\beta], h\beta \in [0, t].$$

(13) shartga ko'ra

$$hD_1[\beta] * V[\beta] = 0, h\beta \notin [0, t].$$

(15)

Ushbu

$$D_1[\beta] = \begin{cases} 0, & |\beta| \geq 2, \\ h^{-2}, & |\beta| = 1, \\ -2h^{-2}, & \beta = 0. \end{cases}$$

operatoridan foydalanib, svyortkani hisoblaymiz

$$D_1[\beta] * V[\beta] = h^{-2}V[\beta-1] - 2h^{-2}V[\beta] + h^{-2}V[\beta+1].$$

Bundan a_0^- va a_0^+ larni aniqlash uchun (15) ga asosan chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasini hosil qilamiz

$$\begin{cases} V[-2] - 2V[-1] + V[0] = 0, \\ V[N] - 2V[N+1] + V[N+2] = 0. \end{cases}$$

Bu yerda

$$V[-2] = a_0^-, V[-1] = a_0^-, V[0] = F_1[0],$$

$$V[N] = F_1[N], V[N+1] = a_0^+, V[N+2] = a_0^+,$$

U holda $a_0^- = F_1[0]$, $a_0^+ = F_1[N]$.

Soddalashtirishlardan so'ng

$$F_1[0] = \frac{t^{\alpha+2}}{2[\alpha+2]!} - \sum_{\gamma=0}^N \frac{\overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\gamma](h\gamma)^2}{4}, \quad (16)$$

$$F_1[N] = \frac{-t^{\alpha+2}}{2[\alpha+2]!} + \sum_{\gamma=0}^N \frac{\overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\gamma](h\gamma)^2}{4}. \quad (17)$$

Bu yerdan quyidagi kelib chiqadi

$$\lambda_1 = \frac{a_0^+ + a_0^-}{2} = 0. \quad (18)$$

$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta]$, $h\beta \in [0, t]$ optimal
koeffitsiyentlarni hisoblashga o'tamiz. $\beta = 0$ bo'lsin,
u holda

$$\begin{aligned} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[0] &= h(D_1[-1]V[-1] + D_1[0]V[0] + D_1[1]V[1]) \\ &= h(h^{-2}F_1[0] - 2h^{-2}F_1[0] + h^{-2}F_1[1]) = h^{-1}(F_1[1] - F_1[0]), \end{aligned}$$

Shunday qilib

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[0] = h^{-1}(F_1[1] - F_1[0]). \quad (19)$$

Shuningdek

$$\begin{aligned} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[N] &= h(D_1[-1]V[N+1] + D_1[0]V[N] + D_1[1]V[N-1]) = \\ &= h(h^{-2}F_1[N] - 2h^{-2}F_1[N] + h^{-2}F_1[N-1]) = h^{-1}(F_1[N-1] - F_1[N]). \end{aligned}$$

Bundan (16) va (17) larga asosan

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[N] = h^{-1}(F_1[N-1] + F_1[0]). \quad (20)$$

$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta]$, $\beta = 1, 2, \dots, N-1$ optimal
koeffitsiyentlarni hisoblaymiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] &= hD_1[\beta] * V[\beta] = h(D_1[-1]V[\beta+1] + D_1[0]V[\beta] + D_1[1]V[\beta-1]) = \\ &= h^{-1}(F_1[\beta+1] - 2F_1[\beta] + F_1[\beta-1]). \end{aligned}$$

Shunday qilib

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] = h^{-1}(F_1[\beta+1] - 2F_1[\beta] + F_1[\beta-1]). \quad (21)$$

Biz quyidagi lemmani isbotladik.

1-lemma. $L_2^{(2)}(0, t)$ fazoda ushbu yagona
optimal kvadratur formula mavjud

$$\int_0^t \frac{\varphi(x)dx}{(t-x)^{1-\alpha}} \cong \sum_{\beta=0}^N \left(\overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta]\varphi[\beta] + \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta]\varphi'[\beta] \right), \quad (22)$$

bu formulaning $\overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta]$ va $\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta]$,
 $\beta = 0, 1, \dots, N$ koeffitsiyentlari (1)-(3) va (19)-(21)
formulalardan aniqlanadi.

$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[0]$ va $\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[N]$ optimal koeffitsiyentlar
uchun oxirgi ifodani olish uchun $F_1[1]$ va $F_1[N-1]$
larni qiymatlarini hisoblaymiz.

(11) formuldan, $\beta = 1$ bo'lganda

$$\begin{aligned} F_1[1] &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=0}^2 \frac{(-1)^{j+1} h^{2-j} t^{\alpha+j}}{(2-j)! [\alpha+j]!} + \frac{(t-h)^{2+\alpha}}{[\alpha+2]!} + \sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] \frac{(h-h\beta)^2 \text{sign}(h-h\beta)}{4} = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{-h^2 t^\alpha}{2\alpha} + \frac{ht^{\alpha+1}}{\alpha(\alpha+1)} - \frac{t^{\alpha+2}}{\alpha(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} \right] + \frac{(t-h)^{2+\alpha}}{[\alpha+2]!} + \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[0] \frac{h^2}{2} - \frac{1}{4} \sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] (h-h\beta)^2. \end{aligned}$$

Bu yerdan

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] = \frac{t^\alpha}{\alpha},$$

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta](h\beta) = \frac{t^{\alpha+1}}{\alpha(\alpha+1)}$$

formulalardan foydalanib, ayrim
soddalashtirishlardan so'ng

$$F_1[1] = \frac{ht^{\alpha+1}}{\alpha(\alpha+1)} - \frac{t^{\alpha+2}}{2[\alpha+2]!} + \frac{(t-h)^{2+\alpha}}{[\alpha+2]!} + \frac{h((t-h)^{\alpha+1} - t^{\alpha+1})}{2\alpha(\alpha+1)} - \frac{1}{4} \sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta](h\beta)^2.$$

U holda (16) va (19) larga asosan

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[0] = h^{-1} \left[\frac{(t-h)^{2+\alpha} - t^{\alpha+2}}{[\alpha+2]!} + \frac{h((t-h)^{\alpha+1} + t^{\alpha+1})}{2[\alpha+1]!} \right]$$

yoki

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[0] = \frac{(t-h)^{2+\alpha} - t^{\alpha+2}}{h[\alpha+2]!} + \frac{(t-h)^{\alpha+1} + t^{\alpha+1}}{2[\alpha+1]!}.$$

(23)

Lopital qoidasini qo'llab, quyidagigi ega bo'lamiz

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[0] = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{(t-h)^{2+\alpha} - t^{\alpha+2}}{h[\alpha+2]!} + \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{(t-h)^{\alpha+1} + t^{\alpha+1}}{2[\alpha+1]!} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{-(t-h)^{\alpha+1}}{[\alpha+1]!} + \frac{t^{\alpha+1}}{[\alpha+1]!} = 0.$$

Demak

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[0] = 0$$

$F_1[N-1]$ ifodani soddalashtirishga o'tamiz.

(11) formulaga asosan, $\beta = N-1$ bo'lganda

$$F_1[N-1] = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=0}^2 \frac{(-1)^{j+1} (h(N-1))^{2-j} t^{\alpha+j}}{(2-j)! [\alpha+j]!} + \frac{(t-h(N-1))^{\alpha+2}}{[\alpha+2]!} +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{4} \sum_{\beta'=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta'] (h(N-1) - h\beta')^2 \text{sign}(h(N-1) - h\beta').$$

$$\text{sign}(h(N-1) - h\beta') \text{ ishorani va } h = \frac{t}{N}$$

ni hisobga olib

$$F_1[N-1] = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{-(t-h)^2 t^\alpha}{2\alpha} + \frac{(t-h)t^{\alpha+1}}{[\alpha+1]!} - \frac{t^{\alpha+2}}{[\alpha+2]!} \right] +$$

$$+ \frac{h^{\alpha+2}}{[\alpha+2]!} - \frac{h^2}{2} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[N] + \frac{1}{4} \sum_{\beta'=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta'] (t-h-h\beta')^2.$$

Bu yerdan

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[N] = \frac{h^\alpha}{\alpha(\alpha+1)}, \quad \sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] = \frac{t^\alpha}{\alpha},$$

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] (h\beta) = \frac{t^{\alpha+1}}{\alpha(\alpha+1)}.$$

formulalarga asosan

$$F_1[N-1] = -\frac{h^{\alpha+2}}{2(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} - \frac{t^{\alpha+2}}{2[\alpha+2]!} + \frac{1}{4} \sum_{\beta'=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta'] (h\beta')^2.$$

(16) ga asosan, (20) formulani quyidagi ko'rinishda yozamiz

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[N] = -\frac{h^{\alpha+1}}{2(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)}.$$

(24)

Ko'rish mumkinki

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[N] = 0.$$

Endi (21) ifodani soddalashtiramiz. Buning uchun (12) formulani quyidagicha yozamiz

$$F_1[\beta] = f_2^{(1)}[\beta] + A[\beta], \quad (25)$$

bunda $\beta = 1, 2, \dots, N-1$. Bu yerda

$$A[\beta] = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{\beta'=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta'] (h\beta - h\beta')^2 \text{sign}(h\beta - h\beta').$$

Ushbu ifodani qaraymiz

$$\begin{aligned} A[\beta+1] - 2A[\beta] + A[\beta-1] &= \frac{1}{4} \sum_{\beta'=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta'] (h(\beta+1) - h\beta')^2 \text{sign}(h(\beta+1) - h\beta') - \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\beta'=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta'] (h\beta - h\beta')^2 \text{sign}(h\beta - h\beta') + \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{4} \sum_{\beta'=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta'] (h(\beta-1) - h\beta')^2 \text{sign}(h(\beta-1) - h\beta'). \end{aligned}$$

Bu yedan $\text{sign}x$ ishorani hisobga olib, ayrim soddalashtirishlardan so'ng

$$\begin{aligned} A[\beta+1] - 2A[\beta] + A[\beta-1] &= \\ &= -\frac{h^2}{2} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\beta'=0}^{\beta} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta'] ((h(\beta+1) - h\beta')^2 - 2(h\beta - h\beta')^2 + (h(\beta-1) - h\beta')^2) - \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{4} \sum_{\beta'=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta'] ((h(\beta+1) - h\beta')^2 - 2(h\beta - h\beta')^2 + (h(\beta-1) - h\beta')^2). \end{aligned}$$

Ko'rish mumkinki

$$(h(\beta+1) - h\beta')^2 - 2(h\beta - h\beta')^2 + (h(\beta-1) - h\beta')^2 = 2h^2.$$

U holda

$$A[\beta+1] - 2A[\beta] + A[\beta-1] = -\frac{h^2}{2} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] + h^2 \sum_{\beta'=0}^{\beta} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta'] - \frac{h^2}{2} \sum_{\beta'=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta'].$$

Bundan (8) ga asosan

$$A[\beta+1] - 2A[\beta] + A[\beta-1] = -\frac{h^2}{2} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] + h^2 \sum_{\beta'=0}^{\beta} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta'] - \frac{h^2 t^\alpha}{2\alpha}.$$

sodda almashtirishlardan so'ng

$$h^2 \sum_{\beta=0}^{\alpha} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] = \frac{h}{\alpha(\alpha+1)} \left((t-h(\beta+1))^{\alpha+1} - (t-h\beta)^{\alpha+1} - (t-h)^{\alpha+1} + t^{\alpha+1} \right).$$

U holda

$$A[\beta+1] - 2A[\beta] + A[\beta-1] = -\frac{h^2}{2} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] + \frac{h^2}{2} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[0] - \frac{h^2 t^{\alpha}}{2\alpha} + \frac{h}{\alpha(\alpha+1)} \left((t-h(\beta+1))^{\alpha+1} - (t-h\beta)^{\alpha+1} - (t-h)^{\alpha+1} + t^{\alpha+1} \right).$$

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[0] \quad \text{va} \quad \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta], \quad \beta = 1, 2, \dots, N-1$$

larni o'rniga (35) va (36) formulalardan aniqlanuvchi ifodalarini qo'yib, quyidagini hosil qilamiz

$$A[\beta+1] - 2A[\beta] + A[\beta-1] = \frac{h}{\alpha(\alpha+1)} \left[\frac{(t-h(\beta+1))^{\alpha+1}}{2} - \frac{(t-h(\beta-1))^{\alpha+1}}{2} \right] + \frac{h^2 t^{\alpha}}{2\alpha}.$$

(26)

Endi ushbu ifodani soddalashtiramiz

$$f_2^{(1)}[\beta+1] - 2f_2^{(1)}[\beta] + f_2^{(1)}[\beta-1] = \frac{1}{[\alpha+2]!} \left[(t-h(\beta+1))^{\alpha+2} - 2(t-h\beta)^{\alpha+2} + (t-h(\beta-1))^{\alpha+2} \right] - \frac{h^2 t^{\alpha}}{2\alpha}.$$

(27)

(25), (26) va (27) formulalardan foydalanib

$$F[\beta+1] - 2F[\beta] + F[\beta-1] = \frac{h}{2\alpha(\alpha+1)} \left[(t-h(\beta+1))^{\alpha+1} - (t-h(\beta-1))^{\alpha+1} \right] +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{[\alpha+2]!} \left[(t-h(\beta+1))^{\alpha+2} - 2(t-h\beta)^{\alpha+2} + (t-h(\beta-1))^{\alpha+2} \right].$$

Bu yerdan (21) formula quyidagi ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] = \frac{1}{2\alpha(\alpha+1)} \left[(t-h(\beta+1))^{\alpha+1} - (t-h(\beta-1))^{\alpha+1} \right] +$$

$$+ \frac{h^{-1}}{[\alpha+2]!} \left[(t-h(\beta+1))^{\alpha+2} - 2(t-h\beta)^{\alpha+2} + (t-h(\beta-1))^{\alpha+2} \right], \quad \beta = 1, 2, \dots, N-1.$$

Ko'rish mumkinki

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] = 0, \quad \beta = 1, 2, \dots, N-1.$$

Biz quyidagi teoremani isbotladik.

1-teorema. Ushbu

$$\int_0^t \frac{\varphi(x) dx}{(t-x)^{1-\alpha}} \cong \sum_{\beta=0}^N \left(C^{(0)}[\beta] \varphi[\beta] + C^{(1)}[\beta] \varphi^1[\beta] \right)$$

kvadratur formulalar ichida $L_2^{(2)}(0, t)$ fazoda koeffitsiyentlari quyidagicha aniqlanadigan yagona optimal kvadratur formula mavjud

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[0] = \frac{1}{h[\alpha+2]!} \left[(t-h)^{\alpha+2} - t^{\alpha+2} \right] + \frac{1}{2[\alpha+1]!} \left[(t-h)^{\alpha+1} + t^{\alpha+1} \right],$$

(28)

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] = \frac{1}{2[\alpha+1]!} \left[(t-h(\beta+1))^{\alpha+1} - (t-h(\beta-1))^{\alpha+1} \right] +$$

$$+ \frac{h^{-1}}{[\alpha+2]!} \left[(t-h(\beta+1))^{\alpha+2} - 2(t-h\beta)^{\alpha+2} + (t-h(\beta-1))^{\alpha+2} \right],$$

(29)

$$\beta = 1, 2, \dots, N-1,$$

$$\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[N] = -\frac{h^{\alpha+1}}{2(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)}, \quad h = \frac{t}{N}, \quad N = 1, 2, \dots,$$

(30)

$$[\alpha+2]! = \alpha(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2).$$

(10) tenglikni hisoblash orqali keltirib chiqarish mumkin, yahni

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] = 0.$$

Belgilash kiritamiz

$$T_1 = \frac{1}{2[\alpha+1]!} \sum_{\beta=1}^{N-1} \left[(t-h(\beta+1))^{\alpha+1} - (t-h(\beta-1))^{\alpha+1} \right],$$

$$T_2 = \frac{h^{-1}}{[\alpha+2]!} \sum_{\beta=1}^{N-1} \left[(t-h(\beta+1))^{\alpha+2} - 2(t-h\beta)^{\alpha+2} + (t-h(\beta-1))^{\alpha+2} \right].$$

Bu yerdan β ni o'rniga ketma-ket $1, 2, \dots, N-1$ larni qo'yib, ayrim soddalashtirishlardan so'ng

$$T_1 = \frac{1}{2[\alpha+1]!} \left(h^{\alpha+1} - t^{\alpha+1} - (t-h)^{\alpha+1} \right),$$

$$T_2 = \frac{h^{-1}}{[\alpha+2]!} \left[-(t-h)^{\alpha+2} - t^{\alpha+2} - h^{\alpha+2} \right].$$

U holda (28)-(30) formulalarga asosan

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] = \frac{h^{-1}}{[\alpha+2]!} \left((t-h)^{\alpha+2} - t^{\alpha+2} \right) + \frac{1}{2[\alpha+1]!} \left((t-h)^{\alpha+1} + t^{\alpha+1} \right) + \frac{1}{2[\alpha+1]!} \left[h^{\alpha+1} - t^{\alpha+1} - (t-h)^{\alpha+1} \right] + \frac{h^{-1}}{[\alpha+2]!} \left(-(t-h)^{\alpha+2} - t^{\alpha+2} - h^{\alpha+2} \right) - \frac{h^{\alpha+1}}{2(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)}$$

Bu yerdan quyidagi kelib chiqadi

$$\sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] = 0.$$

Ushbu teorema o'rinli

2-teorema. (5) ko'rinishdagi optimal kvadratur

formula normasining kvadrati $L_2^{(2)*}(0, t)$ fazoda quyidagi ko'rinishga ega

$$\|t\|_{L_2^{(2)*}}^2 = \sum_{\beta=0}^N \sum_{\beta=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] \left(\overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] \frac{h\beta - h\beta'}{12} - \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] \frac{(h\beta - h\beta')^2 \text{sign}(h\beta - h\beta')}{4} \right)$$

$$+ \sum_{\beta=0}^N \left(\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta] f_2^{(1)}[\beta] - 2 \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta] f_2^{(0)}[\beta] \right) + \frac{t^{2\alpha+3}}{[\alpha+3]!(2\alpha+3)}$$

(31)

Bu yerdan

$f_2^{(0)}[\beta], f_2^{(1)}[\beta], \overset{\circ}{C}^{(0)}[\beta], \overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta], \beta = 0, 1, \dots, N$ lar (1)-(3), (7), (28)-(30) formulalardan aniqlanadi.

Isboti.

Shunday qilib, $\overset{\circ}{C}^{(1)}[\beta], \beta = 0, 1, \dots, N$ optimal koeffitsiyentlar (12) tenglamalar sistemasini qanoatlantiradi, u holda bu tenglikdan foydalanib va (18) ga asosan (6) formula bilan aniqlanuvchi normaning kvadrati uchun ayrim soddalashtirishlardan so'ng (31) ko'rinishga ifodani hosil qilamiz. Bu esa 2-teoremani isbotlaydi.

Sonli natijalar

1-misol. Quyidagi umumlashgan Abel integral tenglamasini yeching

$$\frac{128}{231} x^{\frac{11}{4}} = \int_0^x \frac{1}{(x-t)^{\frac{1}{4}}} \varphi(t) dt.$$

$$\text{Bu yerda } \alpha = \frac{1}{4}, \quad f(x) = \frac{128}{231} x^{\frac{11}{4}}.$$

Ma'lumki, yechim $\varphi(x) = x^2$ ko'rinishda bo'ladi.

$m = 2$ da optimal kvadratur formulalar usuli bilan olingan sonli natijalar

t_i	$N = 1$	$N = 10$	$N = 100$	Aniq yechim	Xatolik $\Delta_{N=100}$
0.1	0.00990824305	0.00999992984	0.00999999985	0.009999999996	1.40(-10)
0.2	0.03963297222	0.03999971946	0.03999999651	0.03999999998	3.47(-9)
0.3	0.08917418742	0.08999936856	0.08999998960	0.08999999995	1.035(-8)

2-misol. Quyidagi umumlashgan Abel integral tenglamasini yeching

$$\frac{432}{935} x^{\frac{17}{6}} = \int_0^x \frac{1}{(x-t)^{\frac{1}{6}}} \varphi(t) dt.$$

$$\text{Bu yerda } \alpha = \frac{1}{6}, \quad f(x) = \frac{432}{935} x^{\frac{17}{6}}.$$

Ma'lumki, yechim $\varphi(x) = x^2$ ko'rinishda bo'ladi.

$m = 2$ da optimal kvadratur formulalar usuli bilan olingan sonli natijalar

t_i	$N = 1$	$N = 10$	$N = 100$	Aniq yechim	Xatolik $\Delta_{N=100}$
0.1	0.009959506131	0.009999975974	0.01000000002	0.010000000000	2.0(-11)
0.2	0.03983802453	0.03999990388	0.03999999874	0.04000000001	1.27(-9)
0.3	0.08963555512	0.08999978366	0.09000000367	0.08999999998	3.69(-9)

3-misol. Quyidagi Abel integral tenglamasini yeching

$$e^x - 1 = \int_0^x \frac{1}{(x-t)^2} \varphi(t) dt.$$

$$\text{Bu yerda } \alpha = \frac{1}{2}, \quad f(x) = e^x - 1.$$

Ma'lumki, yechim

$$\varphi(x) = \frac{e^x}{\sqrt{\pi}} \text{erf}(\sqrt{x}), \quad \text{erf}(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x e^{-t} dt$$

ko'rinishda bo'ladi.

$m = 2$ da optimal kvadratur formulalar usuli bilan olingan sonli natijalar

t_i	$N = 1$	$N = 10$	$N = 100$	Aniq yechim	Xatolik $\Delta_{N=100}$
0.1	.215290815747	.215290502289	.215290502149	.215290502149	1.1(-14)
0.2	.325887541756	.325884078022	.325884076323	.325884076323	5.64(-13)
0.3	.427579571413	.42756566510	.427565657564	.427565657562	2.441(-12)

Xulosa

Qaralayotgan kvadratur formulalarning xatolik funksionali normasining kvadrati hisoblangan. Bu normaning kvadratini koeffisientlar bo'yicha minimallashtirib, qaralayotgan kvadratur formulaning

optimal koeffisientlarini topilgan. $L_2^{(2)}(0, t)$ fazoda optimal kvadratur formulalar qurilgan va ushbu formula normasining kvadrati hisoblangan. Sonli eksperimentlar o'tkazilgan.

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